

Revision of the Genus *Thymalus* (Coleoptera: Cleroidea: Thymalidae) of Japan

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Abstract Japanese species of the genus *Thymalus* Latreille, 1802 are revised. Three species are recognized: *T. amamiensis* Miyatake, 1985, *T. laticeps* Lewis, 1894 (= *T. punctidorsum* Lewis, 1894, syn. nov.), and *T. parviceps* Lewis, 1894. All species are redescribed with illustrations of the taxonomically important characters and photographs of the habitus, and the larvae of *T. laticeps* and *T. parviceps* are described. *Thymalus amamiensis* is newly recorded from Kume-jima, Ryukyus.

Introduction

Since Crowson (1964, 1970), the family Trogossitidae was divided into three independent families (Peltidae, Lophocateridae, and Trogossitidae), and the genus *Thymalus* was treated as a member of the family Peltidae (tribe Thymalini). Kolibáč (2005, 2006, 2013) treated them again as a single family, and recognized four subfamilies (Peltinae, Trogossitinae, Lophocaterinae, and Rentoniinae). Gimmel *et al.* (2019), the first comprehensive molecular phylogenetic study of Cleroidea, elevated some cleroid subfamilies or tribes to family status, and “Trogossitidae” sensu Kolibáč (2005, 2006, 2013) was separated to four families, Peltidae, Lophocateridae, Trogossitidae, and Thymalidae. The family Thymalidae is divided into two subfamilies (Thymalinae and Decamerinae), and belongs to not “trogossitid lineage” but “melyrid lineage”.

The genus *Thymalus* Latreille, 1802 is the monotypic genus of the subfamily Thymalinae, and includes ten described species. Seven species have been recorded from the Palearctic Region, two from the Oriental, and one from the Nearctic Regions (Kolibáč, 2013; Miyatake, 1985; Asakawa & Yoshitomi, 2019).

Up to now, four species of this genus are known from Japan. Three of these, *T. punctidorsum*, *T. laticeps*, and *T. parviceps*, were described by Lewis (1894) from various localities of Mainland Japan. The remaining one, *T. amamiensis*, was described by Miyatake (1985) without detail characters including genital parts.

In this paper, we revise the Japanese species of this genus, with description of larval character of *T. laticeps* and *T. parviceps*. All species are redescribed.

Material and Methods

The specimens examined in this study are preserved in the following institutions and private collections: Natural History Museum, London (BMNH), Ehime University Museum, Matsuyama (EUMJ), Hiwa Museum of Natural Science, Shōbara (HIWA), National Museum of Nature & Science, Tsukuba (NSMT), and Katsumi Akita’s private collection, Tsu (KAC).

The method of general observation and dissection follows Yoshitomi & Lee (2014). Microstructures of dissected parts

were studied in pure glycerin under an Olympus BH-2 compound microscope. After observation, the dissected parts were mounted on the same card with the specimen. The terminology refers generally to Kolibáč (2005) and Yoshitomi (2014).

The rearing method of the adults of *T. laticeps* follows Kimura (1995).

Abbreviations used in this paper are as follows: EL (length of elytra at suture); EW (maximum width of elytra); PL (maximum length of pronotum); PW (maximum width of pronotum); TL (total length: PL+EL). The arithmetic mean is given in parentheses after the range.

Collector names of the specimens examined are abbreviated as follows: AO: A. Oda; AS: A. Sasai; AY: A. Yonetsu; CT: C. Takahashi; EY: E. Yamamoto; GT: G. Tokihiro; HK: H. Kusunoki; HKA: H. Kan; HKO: H. Kōno; HT: H. Takabayashi; HY: H. Yoshitomi; JO: J. Okayasu; JY: J. Yamasako; KA: K. Akita; KAI: K. Aita; KAN: K. Ando; KE: K. Emoto; KF: K. Fukuzumi; KM: K. Masumoto; KO: K. Okada; KS: K. Sogoh; KT: K. Takahashi; KY: K. Yasumatsu; KYO: K. Yoshida; MK: M. Kawanabe; MKO: M. Kotani; MM: M. Miyatake; MN: M. Nishi; MS: M. Sakai; MSA: M. Satō; MT: M. Tomokuni; MY: M. Yoshikura; MYO: M. Yoshida; NO: N. Ohbayashi; RI: R. Ito; RK: R. Koga; RM: R. Masaoka; RMA: R. Matsuda; RO: R. Ogawa; ROK: R. Okano; SH: S. Hisamatsu; SHI: S. Hisamatsu; SK: S. Kinoshita; SN: S. Nagai; SNA: S. Nakamura; ST: S. Tsuyuki; STA: S. Tanaka; SY: S. Yoshimichi; SYA: S. Yamamoto; TA: T. Abe; TE: T. Esaki; TED: T. Edashige; TI: T. Imamura; TIC: T. Ichianagi; TIS: T. Ishihara; TIT: T. Ito; TK: T. Kitano; TM: T. Miyata; TMA: T. Matsuda; TMI: T. Miyamoto; TY: T. Yoro; TYA: T. Yano; TYO: T. Yoshida; YH: Y. Hara; YN: Y. Notsu; YS: Y. Seiyama; YU: Y. Utsunomiya.

Taxonomy

Family Thymalidae Lèveillé, 1888
Subfamily Thymalinae Lèveillé, 1888
Genus *Thymalus* Latreille, 1802

Thymalus Latreille, 1802: 133 [original description]; Böving & Craighead, 1931: 274–275 (pl. 94 P–U; larvae); Crowson, 1964: 296 [key to larva]; Kolibáč, 2005: 85 [adult description]; Kolibáč, 2006: 110 [larval description]; Kolibáč, 2013: 115 [catalogued]; Gimmel *et*

Fig. 1. Habitus of *Thymalus* spp. A–C, *Thymalus laticeps*; D–F, *T. amamiensis* (holotype); G–I, *T. parviceps*. A, D, G, Dorsal view; B, E, H, lateral view; C, F, I, punctures on pronotum. Scales = 1.0 mm.

al., 2019: 527 [valid genus].

Type species. *Peltis brunnea* Thunberg, 1794 (by monotypy).

Diagnosis. Adults. Body semicircular, hemispherical (=

cassidine-like in Gimmel *et al.*, 2019); dorsal surface covered with dense long pubescence (but lacking in *T. yamasakoi* and old individuals); head covered by pronotum; labrum (Fig. 3A, B) with arcuate anterior margin, as long as wide; mandible (Fig. 3C, D) with two apical teeth; lacinia (Fig. 3E) with 2

Fig. 2. Type materials of *Thymalus* spp. preserved in BMNH. A–C, *Thymalus laticeps* Lewis; D–F, *Thymalus punctidorsum* Lewis; G–I, *Thymalus parviceps* Lewis. A, D, G, Habitus; B, E, H, head and pronotum; C, F, I, labels. Photos by Senda.

hooked thorns (Kolibáč, 2005); terminal segment of labial palpus (Fig. 3F) coniform; antennae (Fig. 4) 11-segmented; pronotum with rounded anterior angles; procoxa transverse; elytra without carinae, confusedly punctate; hind wing (Fig. 3G) fully developed; parameres fused tegmen.

Larvae. Body weakly sclerotized except for head, pronotum, and abdominal segment IX, bearing long setae; head lacking dorsal endocarina and ventral epicranial ridges; antennomere I (Figs. 8C, 10C) transverse; urogomphi (Figs. 7E–G, 9E–G) large, with six (dorsal (d), lateral (l), apical (a), subapical (s), interior (i), and ventral (v)) projections.

Remarks. This genus is similar to trogossitid genera *Ancyrona* (Lophocateridae) and *Peltis* (Peltidae) in the general feature, but differs from them by the following characteristics: body hemispherical (flattened in *Ancyrona* and *Peltis*); head covered with pronotum (visible dorsally in *Ancyrona* and *Peltis*); elytra without carinae (with distinct carinae in *Peltis*, with indistinct carinae in *Ancyrona*).

Distribution. Palearctic, Nearctic, and Oriental Regions.

Biological notes. The beetles are not associated with any particular tree species, and are found on both deciduous and

coniferous trees (Kolibáč, 2013). The larvae and adults are mycophagous, and collected from Polypores. It is assumed that the larvae feed on fungi in rotten or decaying wood (Kolibáč, 2006, 2013).

Key to species of the genus *Thymalus* in Japan

1. Body with strong metallic luster; pronotum irregularly, roughly and sparsely punctate; phallus more or less pointed in apical portion. 2
- Body with very weak metallic luster; pronotum finely and densely punctate; phallus extremely rounded in apical portion. *T. laticeps* Lewis
2. Coloration brown to dark brown; tegmen and phallus relatively short. *T. parviceps* Lewis
- Coloration light brown; tegmen and phallus very long. *T. amamiensis* Miyatake

***Thymalus amamiensis* Miyatake, 1985**

[Japanese name: Amami-sedaka-kokunusuto]

(Figs. 1D–F, 4A, B, 5O–R, 6A–C)

Fig. 3. Mouth parts (A–F) and hindwing venation (G) of *Thymalus parviceps* Lewis. A, B, Labrum; C, D, right mandible; E, maxilla; F, labial palpus. A, C, dorsal view; B, D, E, F, ventral view.

Thymalus amamiensis Miyatake, 1985: 149, pl. 24 [original description]; Oogai, 2014: 44 [distribution: Okinawa-jima].

Type specimen examined. Holotype: 1 female (EUMJ), “Mt. Yuwan Amami-Oshima 19. IV. 1971 M. Sakai leg.,” “8-06” (orange label, plate no. of Miyatake, 1985), “HOLOTYPE *Thymalus amamiensis* Miyatake, 1985 DET. Asakawa & Yoshitomi 2019”.

Other specimens examined. [Kagoshima Pref., Amami-Ōshima] 1 ex., Akafusa-rindō, Sumiyō-chō, Amami-shi, 6.

XII. 2012, MN (KAC); 2 exs., Higahinakama, Sumiyō-chō, Amami-shi, 17. V. 2014, MN (KAC); 1 ex., same loc., 2. VII. 2017, MN (KAC); 1 female, 1 ex., Kawauchi, Sumiyō-chō, Amami-shi, 25. VI. 2016, MN (KAC); 1 ex., Santarō-tōge, Sumiyō-chō, Amami-shi, 2–4. V. 2010, KM & KT (KAC); 1 male, 1 ex., Takabachi-yama, Sumiyō-chō, 20. VI. 2015, MN (KAC); 1 ex., Uragami, Naze, Amami-shi, 1. VII. 2017, MN (KAC); 1 ex., Kominato, Naze, Amami-shi, 15. VI. 2017, MN (KAC); 1 ex., same loc., 21. IX. 2016, MN (KAC); 1 male, Akatsuchi-yama, Uken-son 1. V. 1999, MS

Fig. 4. Antennae of *Thymalus* spp. A, B, *Thymalus amamiensis* Miyatake; C, D, *T. laticeps* Lewis; E, F, *T. parviceps* Lewis. A, C, E, Male; B, D, F, female.

(EUMJ); 2 exs., Yuwan-dake, Uken-son, 5. VII. 1999, KA (KAC); 2 exs., Aminoko-tôge, Setouchi-chô, 12. V. 2012, MN (KAC); 1 female, same loc., 13. V. 2013, MN (KAC); 1 female, Hatsuno, Setouchi-chô, 2. V. 1977, AO (EUMJ); 1 ex., Yui-dake, Setouchi-chô, 3. XI. 2016, MN (KAC); 2 males, 3 females, same loc., 17. IV. 1971, MS (EUMJ); 1 ex., Chûô-rindô, 27. III. 1999, NO (EUMJ). [Okinawa Pref., Kume-jima] 1 ex., Âra-dake, 21. III. 2010, KAN (EUMJ).

Redescription. Male. Body (Fig. 1D, E) semicircular, convex dorsally, flat ventrally, with strong metallic luster. Coloration of body light brown to dark brown in dorsal surface, light yellowish brown in ventral surface; lateral margin transparent yellowish brown; antennomeres 9–11 dark brown.

Head roughly and irregularly punctate; vertex convex. Eyes relatively large, situated in lateral part of head. Antennae (Fig. 4A, B) relatively long; antennomere I longest, strongly curved interiorly, projecting in apical 1/3 of outer margin;

antennomeres III about 2.0 times as long as wide respectively; antennomere VIII transverse, projecting laterally; antennomeres IX–XI densely covered with short setae and sparsely with long setae; antennomere XI semicircular; approximate ratio of each antennomere ($n = 1$) as 7.6 : 2.6 : 2.4 : 1.6 : 1.6 : 1.6 : 1.6 : 1.2 : 1.0 : 2.4 : 2.4 : 4.0. Pronotum (Fig. 1F) irregularly, roughly and sparsely punctate, irregularly and sparsely bearing short setae in mesal portion; lateral margins weakly upturned, bearing many setae; anterior angle rounded, strongly curved in distal portion; PW/PL 1.88–2.67 (2.23). Elytra regularly and roughly punctate, widest at the middle, densely bearing long setae; lateral margins upturned, rounded in distal portion; EL/EW 0.89–1.19 (1.10); EL/PL 3.13–4.42 (3.67); EW/PW 1.35–1.67 (1.50); TL/EW 1.15–1.57 (1.40). Abdominal ventrite V densely bearing long setae.

Tergite VIII well sclerotized, trapezoidal, bearing short setae, arcuate in posterior margin. Sternite VIII slightly sclerotized, bearing setae of irregular length, arcuate in

Fig. 5. Male genitalia of *Thymalus* spp. A–G, *Thymalus laticeps* Lewis; H–N, *T. parviceps* Lewis; O–R, *T. amamiensis* Miyatake. A, H, Tergite VIII; B, I, sternite VIII; C, J, segments IX–X; D, E, K, L, O, P, tegmen; F, G, M, N, Q, R, phallus. D, G, K, N, O, R, dorsal view; E, L, P, ventral view; F, M, Q, lateral view.

posterior margin. Segments IX–X with long and slender median strut; posterior margin of segment X arcuate. Tegmen (Fig. 5O, P) long; phallobasic apodeme Y-shaped, long; tegminal strut long, widened basally; parameral piece short,

clearly shorter than tegminal strut, bearing short setae, arcuate in apical margin. Phallus (Fig. 5Q, R) long, longer than tegmen, gently arcuate in dorsal margin, straight in ventral margin, sharply pointed at apex, widest at basal 1/3.

Fig. 6. Female genitalia of *Thymalus* spp. A–C, *Thymalus amamiensis* Miyatake; D–F, *T. parviceps* Lewis; G–J, *T. laticeps* Lewis. A, D, G, Tergite VIII; B, E, H, sternite VIII; C, F, I, ovipositor; J, spermatheca.

Female. Sexual dimorphism indistinct; abdominal ventrite V sparsely bearing short setae; approximate ratio of each antennomere ($n = 1$) as 6.7 : 2.5 : 1.7 : 1.5 : 1.5 : 1.2 : 1.0 : 1.0 : 2.2 : 1.8 : 3.5. Tergite VIII (Fig. 6A) well sclerotized,

trapezoidal, arcuate in posterior margin, bearing short setae. Sternite VIII (Fig. 6B) moderately sclerotized, semicircular, shallowly concave in posterior margin; spiculum relatively short. Ovipositor (Fig. 6C) relatively short; approximate ratio

of stylus, coxite, and baculus (n = 1) as 1.0 : 3.6 : 8.0.

Measurements (n = 10). TL 6.40–7.50 (6.96) mm; PW 3.00–4.00 (3.33) mm; PL 1.20–1.70 (1.50) mm; EL 5.00–5.80 (5.46) mm; EW 4.20–6.50 (5.00) mm.

Remarks. This species is closely related to *T. parviceps*, but is distinguished from the latter by the light brown body coloration, strong metallic luster on dorsal surface, sparse punctures in pronotum and long and sharply pointed phallus.

The late Dr. Mutsuo Miyatake described 19 new species in the book “Kurosawa Y., S. Hisamatsu & H. Sasaji (eds.) The Coleoptera of Japan in Color, 3, 514 pp. Hoikusha, Osaka”, but their descriptions were incomplete and the type data were not shown in the descriptions. Judging from the redescriptions of some species (Kawanabe & Miyatake, 1996; Sato, 2002), he designated the holotypes as the figured specimens in the book. The holotype of *Thymalus amamiensis* was not attached the type label, however it was cleared that the female specimen figured in the book was the holotype.

Distribution. Ryukyus (Amami-Ōshima; Okinawa-jima; Kume-jima — new record).

Biological notes. This species seems to be rare, and the biological information is scarce.

Thymalus laticeps Lewis, 1894

[Japanese name: Oozu-sedaka-kokunusuto]

(Figs. 1A–C, 2A–F, 4C, D, 5A–G, 6G–I, 7, 8, 11E, F)

Thymalus laticeps Lewis, 1894: 33 [original description]; Hayashi, 1952: 12 [description of larva]; Nakane, 1963: 181, pl. 91-6 [characters; habitus photo]; Miyatake, 1985: 149, pl. 24 [characters; habitus photo].

Thymalus punctidorsum Lewis, 1894: 33 [original description]; Nakane, 1963: 181, pl. 91-7 [characters; habitus photo]; Miyatake, 1985: 149 [characters; habitus photo]. Syn. nov.

Type specimens examined. Syntype of *Thymalus laticeps*: 1 female (BMNH, Fig. 2A–C), “LECTO-TYPE”, “SYN-TYPE”, “Type”, “Fuji”, “Japan. G. Lewis. 1910-320.”, “*Thymalus laticeps* Type. Lewis”, “Lectotypus *Thymalus laticeps* Lewis Designated by N. Nikitsky, 1998”. Holotype of *Thymalus punctidorsum*: 1 female (BMNH, Fig. 2D–F), “Holo-type”, “Type”, “Japan. G. Lewis. 1910-320”, “*Thymalus punctidorsus* Type. Lewis”, “Holotypus *Thymalus punctidorsus* Lewis designated by N. Nikitsky, 1998”.

Other specimens examined. <HOKKAIDO> 1 ex., Sapporo, HKO (NSMT). <HONSHU> [Miyagi Pref.] 1 ex., Funagata-yama, Kami-machi, 10. IX. 2009, RI (KAC). [Fukushima Pref.] 1 ex., Kojikishi-rindō, Haramachi-shi, 2. VI. 1991, KE (KAC). [Tochigi Pref.] 1 ex., Chuzenji-Yumoto, Nikko-shi, 22. VII. 1923, TE (EUMJ); 2 exs., Yumoto, Nikko-shi, 11. XII. 2010, YU (KAC); 1 ex., same loc., 27. VIII. 2010, YU (KAC); 1 ex., Kuriyama, 15. V. 2010, KA & KT (KAC); 1 ex., Nasu, 29. VII. 1956, SH (EUMJ). [Gunma Pref.] 1 ex., Hotaka-san, Minakami-machi, 19. VIII. 1973, ST (NSMT); 1 ex., Tanigawa-dake, 2. VII. 1950, SH (EUMJ). [Tokyo Pref.] 1 ex., Takao-san, Hachiōji-shi, 5. VIII., HT (NSMT, Det. H. Kono. H. Kono collection); 5 exs., same

loc., 20. IX. 2012, SYA (EUMJ); 1 ex., Tenso-san, Okutama-machi, 15. VI. 1977, MT (EUMJ). [Kanagawa Pref.] 1 ex., Ō-yama, Sagami, 26. IV. 1953, TY (KAC). [Nagano Pref.] 6 exs., Jumonji-yama, Kawakami-mura, 11. VIII. 1985, AS & TA (KAC); 4 exs., Kiso-fukushima, Kiso-gun, 22. VII. 1993, HY (EUMJ). [Yamanashi Pref.] 2 exs., Aokigahara, Fuji, 12. VII. 1981, ST (NSMT); 1 ex., Ōdarumi-tōge, Makiokachō, 23. VII. 1992, KA (KAC). [Mie Pref.] 1 ex., Hirakura, Misugi-mura, 21. IX. 1986, KA (KAC); 1 ex., same loc., 27. V. 1988, KA (KAC); 1 ex., same loc., 8. IX. 1996, KA (KAC). [Kyoto Pref.] 2 exs., Kuramakifune-chō, 12. VII. 1970, MT (EUMJ), 3 exs., same loc., 25. VI. 1965, MT (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 12. VII. 1970, KAN (EUMJ). [Nara Pref.] 2 exs., Kasuga-yama, Nara-shi, 10. X. 1984, KAN (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 26. VI. 1999, KA (KAC); 1 ex., same loc., 3. VI. 2001, KA (KAC); 1 ex., same loc., 13. VI. 2004, KA (KAC); 1 ex., same loc., 21. V. 2005, KA (KAC); 4 exs., same loc., 24. VI. 2006, KA (KAC); 1 ex., same loc., 26. VI. 2008, KA (KAC); 6 exs., same loc., 27. V. 2009, KA (KAC); 1 ex., same loc., 4. VI. 2011, KA (KAC). [Hyogo Pref.] 1 ex., Akasai, Haga-chō, 12. V. 1985, KAN (EUMJ). [Okayama Pref.] 1 ex., Gagyū-zan, Takahashi-shi, 14. VIII. 1978, MM (EUMJ). [Hiroshima Pref.] 1 ex., Nukui, Kake, Akiōta-chō, 12. VIII. 2007, (HIWA); 3 exs., same loc., 8. VIII. 2007, (HIWA). [Yamaguchi Pref.] 1 ex., Jakuchi-kyō, Nishikimachi, Iwakuni-shi, 22. VI. 2015, STA (KAC); 2 exs., same loc., 4. VI. 2015, STA (KAC); 1 ex., Nagano-yama, Shūnan-shi, 20. XI. 2015, STA (KAC). <SHIKOKU> [Tokushima Pref.] 1 ex., Miune, Higashiiyayama-son, 22. VII. 1997, KA (KAC); 1 ex., Nagayasu, Naka-chō, 24. VI. 2009, YU (EUMJ). [Ehime Pref.] 2 exs., Besshiyama-mura, 29. VII. 1954, TYA (EUMJ); 2 exs., Narabara-san, Imabari-shi, 16. IV. 2017, JO (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 16. IV. 2017, TMI (EUMJ). 1 ex., same loc., 16. IV. 2017, RK (EUMJ); 1 ex., Komenono, Matuyama-shi, 27. V. 1970, GT (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 24. IX. 1973, MT (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 18. VII. 1975, AY (EUMJ); 1 ex., Takanawa-san, Matsuyama-shi, 25. V. 2007, TK (EUMJ); 3 exs., same loc., 27. IX. 2007, TIC (EUMJ); 5 exs., same loc., 25. X. 1953, HK (EUMJ; from Fomes sp.); 1 ex., same loc., 18. IX. 2005, JY (EUMJ); 3 exs., same loc., 15. VII. 1956, HK (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 1. IX. 2016, KS (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 3. XI. 2016, TIT (EUMJ); 1 ex., Shiratsue, Shigenobu-chō, 9. VII. 1972, SK (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 26. V. 1979, YS (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 24. VIII. 1993, KO (EUMJ); 1 ex., Ishizuchi-san, Kumakōgen-chō, 24. V. 2005, TK (EUMJ); 4 exs., same loc., 16. VII. 2017, KS (EUMJ); 3 exs., Omogo-kei, Omogo-mura, 8. IX. 1951, SH (EUMJ, Det. T. Nakane 1953); 1 ex., same loc., 1. VI. 1954, MM (EUMJ); 2 exs., same loc., 25. VIII. 1954, TED (EUMJ); 6 exs., same loc., 26. VI. 1955, SH (EUMJ); 3 exs., same loc., 20. V. 1956, SH (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 17. VI. 1956, MM (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 21. VII. 1958, MM (EUMJ); 2 exs., same loc., 25. V. 1959, SH (EUMJ); 3 exs., same loc., 21. X. 1959, MM (EUMJ); 2 exs., same loc., 18–19. V. 1968, MS (EUMJ); 5 exs., same loc., 24. VI. 1971, MS (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 19. VIII. 1975, AO (EUMJ); 7 exs., same loc., 2. V. 1976, AO (EUMJ); 3 exs., same loc., 29. V. 1977, AO (EUMJ); 9 exs., same loc., 2. X. 1977, AO (EUMJ); 2 exs.,

Fig. 7. Larva of *Thymalus laticeps* Lewis. A, Habitus; B–D, head; E–G, urogomphi. Dorsal (A, B, E), ventral (C, F), and lateral (D, G) views.

same loc., 20. IV. 1992, MS (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 15. IV. 1993, MS (EUMJ); 3 exs., same loc., 15. IX. 1993, SH & SHI (EUMJ); 5 exs., same loc., 15. IX. 1993, MS (EUMJ); 1 ex., Saragamine, Kumakôgen-chô, 12. VII. 2008, YH (EUMJ); 1 ex., Odamiyama, Oda-chô, 5. V. 1974, HKA (EUMJ); 1 ex., Narukawa, Hiromi-chô, 4. V. 1992, MS (EUMJ). <KYUSHU> [Fukuoka Pref.] 1 ex., Hiko-san, Hikosan-mura, 16. V. 1938, KY (EUMJ); 2 exs., same loc., 7. VII. 1957, MM (EUMJ); 1 ex., Hei-zan, Amagi-shi, 22. IX. 1993, (EUMJ); 1 ex., Kosho-san, Amagi-shi, 19. IV. 1997, (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 26. VII. 1989, (EUMJ). [Saga Pref.] 1 ex., “Saga”, MY (NSMT, H. Kono collection). [Oita Pref.] 1 ex., Kuro-dake, Shonai-chô, 16. VI. 1979, SN (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 15. VII. 1984, (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 30. VII. 1986, (EUMJ); 2 exs., same loc., 2. X. 1989, (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 31. VII. 1990, (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 27. V. 1995, (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 13. IX. 1997, (EUMJ); 7 exs., same loc., 2. X. 2008, TIC (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 2. X. 2009, RO (EUMJ); 5 exs., Kumamure-yama, Yufu-shi, 2. V. 2019, KYO (EUMJ); 5 exs., Obira-kôzan, Ogata-machi, 30. VII. 2017, RI (KAC); 1 ex., same loc., 10. IX. 2017, RI (KAC); 2 exs., Takadoya-jinja, Minamitabarû, Ume, Saiki-shi, 21. IX. 2016, RI (KAC); 1 ex.,

same loc., 23. IX. 2016, RI (KAC); 1 ex., same loc., 3. VI. 2016, RI (KAC); 3 exs., same loc., 10. VI. 2016, RI (KAC); 1 ex., same loc., 27. V. 2016, RI (KAC); 2 exs., same loc., 21. IX. 2018, RI (KAC). [Kumamoto Pref.] 9 exs., Ichifusayama, Mizukami-mura, 9. VI. 1967, SH (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 12. XI. 1967, SH (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 11. VI. 1972, SH (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 16. VIII. 1977, (EUMJ); 1 ex., Shiraga-dake, 28. IX. 1997, (EUMJ). [Miyazaki Pref.] 3 males, 3 females, Miike, Takaharu-chô, 27–28. V. 2006, KAN (EUMJ); 2 exs., Mukôzaka-yama, Gokase-chô, 17. VI. 2017, RI (KAC). [Kagoshima Pref.] 1 ex., Kurino-dake, Kurino-chô, 15. VI. 1972, SH (EUMJ); 2 exs., same loc., 28. VII. 1975, MS (NSMT).

Specimens examined of larvae. 2 exs. (EUMJ, in ethanol), Kenashi-yama, Unnan-shi, Shimane Pref., Japan, 6. XI. 2017, HY. (Eight individuals of larvae were reared with host fungus and the adults were emerged in January 2018.)

Redescription. Male. Body (Fig. 1A, B) semicircular, relatively convex dorsally, flat ventrally, with very weak metallic luster. Coloration of body brown in dorsal surface, black in ventral surface; lateral margin transparent dark reddish brown; antennomere 9–11 black.

Fig. 8. Larva of *Thymalus laticeps* Lewis. A, Left mandible in ventral view; B, maxillae and labium in ventral view; C, antenna; D, labrum in dorsal view; E, epipharynx.

Head finely and sparsely punctate; vertex convex. Eyes relatively large, situated in lateral part of head. Antennae (Fig. 4C, D) relatively long; antennomere I longest, strongly curved interiorly, projecting in apical 1/3 of outer margin; antennomeres III–V about 2.0 times as long as wide respectively; antennomere VIII transverse, strongly projecting laterally; antennomeres IX–XI densely covered with short setae and sparsely with long setae; antennomere XI semicircular; approximate ratio of each antennomere ($n = 1$) as 7.2 : 1.8 : 1.8 : 1.3 : 1.3 : 1.2 : 1.2 : 1.0 : 2.0 : 2.0 : 2.8. Pronotum (Fig. 1F) irregularly, finely and densely punctate, irregularly and sparsely bearing short setae in mesal portion; lateral margins weakly upturned; anterior angle rounded; PW/PL 1.50–2.93 (2.22). Elytra roughly and regularly punctate, widest at apical 1/3, bearing short setae; lateral margins upturned, rounded in distal portion; EL/EW 1.16–1.19 (1.17); EL/PL 2.40–4.50 (3.52); EW/PW 1.29–1.46 (1.36); TL/EW 1.43–1.67 (1.52). Abdominal ventrite V densely bearing long setae.

Tergite VIII (Fig. 5A) well sclerotized, trapezoidal, bearing setae of irregular length, shallowly concave at posterior margin. Sternite VIII (Fig. 5B) slightly sclerotized, bearing setae of irregular length, almost straight at posterior margin. Segments IX–X (Fig. 5C) with relatively short median strut; posterior margin of segment X excised. Tegmen (Fig.

5D, E) short; phallobasic apodeme U-shaped, short; tegminal strut short, subparallel-sided; parameral piece long, as long as tegminal strut, bearing short setae, shallowly excised at apical margin. Phallus (Fig. 5F, G) short, a little shorter than tegmen, gently arcuate in dorsal and ventral margins, rounded at apex, widest at the middle.

Female. Sexual dimorphism indistinct; abdominal ventrite V sparsely bearing short setae; approximate ratio of each antennomere ($n = 1$) as 7.1 : 2.0 : 1.6 : 1.6 : 1.4 : 1.3 : 1.1 : 1.0 : 2.0 : 2.0 : 3.0. Tergite VIII (Fig. 6G) well sclerotized, semicircular, rounded in posterior margin, bearing long setae. Sternite VIII (Fig. 6H) moderately sclerotized, semicircular; spiculum long. Ovipositor (Fig. 6I) long; stylus oblong, bearing setae of irregular length; approximate ratio of stylus, coxite, and baculus ($n = 1$) as 1.0 : 6.3 : 8.7. Spermatheca (Fig. 6J) oval.

Measurements. ($n = 10$): TL 7.60–9.50 (8.30) mm; PW 3.50–4.20 (4.03) mm; PL 1.40–2.80 (1.89) mm; EL 6.00–6.70 (6.41) mm; EW 5.10–5.80 (5.46) mm.

Larvae (Figs. 7A, 11E). Body somewhat thick, cylindrical, cream, weakly sclerotized except for well sclerotized head, mesal part of pronotum, and abdominal segment IX. Head (Fig. 7B–D) well sclerotized, with five pairs of stemmata in antero-lateral parts. Mandibles (Fig. 8A) with two blunt apical teeth. Labrum (Fig. 8D, E) transverse, bearing four pairs of

setae; epipharynx with row of stout setae on anterior margin, with short setae and pores in mesal part. Antennae (Fig. 8C) 3-segmented; antennomere II transverse; antennomere III long, with a long apical spine; sensory appendix long, coniform. Labium (Fig. 8B) transverse, with 2-segmented palpi. Prothorax (Fig. 7A) well sclerotized, bearing long setae in lateral parts. Meso- and Metathorax (Fig. 7A) wider than prothorax, with seven pairs of short setae and three pairs of long setae. Abdomen (Fig. 7A) bearing 9–14 pairs of setae; two lateral and one dorsal setae very long. Abdominal segment IX well sclerotized, densely bearing setae of irregular length. Urogomphi (Fig. 7E–G) relatively long, having six projections; dorsal projection (d) short and oval, situated in basal part of dorsal surface, with a long seta; lateral projection (l) projecting postero-laterally, bearing a long seta; apical projection (a) longest, pointed at apex, projecting posteriorly, upturned in apical part, bearing short seta; subapical projection (s) long, pointed at apex, situated in ventral part of apical projection, with a long seta; interior projection (i) short, projecting interiorly; ventral projection (v) short, situated in base of subapical projection of ventral surface, bearing long seta.

Remarks. Lewis (1894) distinguished *T. punctidorsum* from *T. laticeps* by the following characteristics: antennomere I not widened laterally; head and pronotum distinctly punctate; elytral punctures deep and closely set together, its nodules well raised. However these characteristics are variable, and we cannot clearly separate them including the holotype of *T. punctidorsum*. In this paper, we treat *T. punctidorsum* as a junior synonym of *T. laticeps*.

The larva of this species differs from the larva of *T. parviceps* Lewis, 1894 by the following characteristics: body somewhat thick; secondary setae in dorsal surface of abdomen few; each urogomphus rather long, close each other; dorsal projection of urogomphus bearing a long seta. The larvae of *T. marginicollis* Chevrolat, 1842 and *T. limbatus* Fabricius, 1787 were figured by Böving & Craighead (1931), and these larvae are similar to that of *T. laticeps* judging from the shape of urogomphi (each urogomphus rather long, close each other). However, the larva of *T. limbatus* figured and described by Kolibáč (2006) has not similar shape of urogomphi (each urogomphus rather short, separated each other).

Distribution. Japan (Hokkaido, Honshu, Shikoku, and Kyushu).

Biological notes. Hayashi (1950, 1952) noted the host fungus of this species is *Fomitopsis pinicola*; the larva lives on under surface of body of the fungus, makes spherical pupal chamber and pupate in late May, and the adult emerge in late June. In Shimane Prefecture, the larva lives on the body of host fungus (probably *Ganoderma applanatum*) attached wood of *Acer* sp. in November. In rearing condition, the adults eat plain bread and powder of dry yeast (Fig. 11F) and live in long period (ca. three months or more). Overwintering is probably occurred in both adult and larval stages.

***Thymalus parviceps* Lewis, 1894**

[Japanese name: Sedaka-kokunusuto]

(Figs. 1G–I, 2G–I, 3, 4E, F, 5H–N, 6D–F, 9, 10, 11A–D)

Thymalus parviceps Lewis, 1894: 33. Nakane, 1963: 181, pl. 91-5; Miyatake, 1985: 149, pl. 24; Chûjô & Lee, 1994: 188; Suzuki, 2009: 38 [figure of larva].

Type specimen examined. Syntype, 1 male (BMNH): “LECTOTYPE”, “Type”, “SYNTYPE”, “Chiuzenji. 19. VIII. -24. VIII. 81.”, “Japan. G. Lewis. 1910-320”, “*Thymalus parviceps* Type. Lewis”, “Lectotypus *Thymalus parviceps* Lewis det. Nikitsky, 1998”.

Other specimens examined. <HOKKAIDO> 1 ex., Rausu-dake, Rausu-chô, 1. VIII. 1990, TI (KAC); 1 ex., Kawayu, Teshikaga-chô, 22. VII. 1970, MS (EUMJ); 1 ex., Onnenai, Tsurui-mura, 24. VIII. 1990, MS (EUMJ); 1 ex., Kirakotan-misaki, Tsurui-mura, 25. VIII. 1990, MS (EUMJ); 1 ex., Ashoro-mura, 30. VII. 1949, RMA (EUMJ); 2 exs., Midorigaoka, Obihiro-shi, 24. VIII. 1995, SH (EUMJ); 3 exs., Seika, Taiki-chô, 5. IX. 2010, KA (KAC); 1 ex., Kiyokawa, Kamikawa-chô, 17. IX. 2013, SYA (EUMJ); 4 exs., Nopporo, Ebetsu-shi, 16. VIII. 1991, TM (KAC). <HONSHU> [Aomori Pref.] 11 exs., Higashidôri-mura, Shimokita, 19. IX. 2018, RO (EUMJ). [Tochigi Pref.] 1 ex., Chuzenji, Nikko-shi, 28. VII. 1993, MK (EUMJ); 3 exs., Yumoto, Nikko-shi, 24. VII. 1958, SH (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 29. VII. 1993, MK (EUMJ); 1 ex., Nasu, 12. VIII. 1948, SH (EUMJ); 2 exs., same loc., 15. VIII. 1948, SH (NSMT); 1 ex., same loc., 17. VIII. 1948, SH (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 2. IX. 1948, SH (EUMJ). [Kanagawa Pref.] 2 exs., Otome-tôge, Hakone-chô, 28. VIII. 1996, SH (EUMJ). [Nagano Pref.] 1 ex., Kiso-fukushima, Kiso-gun, 7. VII. 1991, HY (EUMJ); 1 ex., Kurosawa, Mitake-mura, 29. VII. 1995, HY (EUMJ); 1 ex., Mitsukai-yama, Takatô-machi, 4. VI. 2005, KA (KAC); 1 ex., Tobira, Iriyamabe, Mastumotoshi, 31. VII. 1973, SH (EUMJ); 1 ex., Shirakoma-no-ike, Koumi-machi, 22. VII. 2005, KA (KAC). [Aichi Pref.] 1 ex., Uradani, Damine, Shitara-chô, 28. VII. 1992, HY (EUMJ). [Mie Pref.] 1 ex., Akame-chô, Nabari-shi, 5. V. 1998, KA (KAC); 1 ex., Asake-keikoku, Komono-chô, 13. VI. 1992, KA (KAC); 2 exs., Hirakura, Misugi-mura, 22. VI. 1986, KA (KAC); 1 ex., same loc., 26. VII. 1987, KA (KAC); 1 ex., same loc., 28. VI. 1987, KA (KAC); 1 ex., same loc., 27. V. 1988, KA (KAC); 1 ex., same loc., 30. VI. 1990, KA (KAC); 1 ex., same loc., 2. X. 1990, KA (KAC); 1 ex., same loc., 9. X. 1990, KA (KAC); 1 ex., same loc., 3. X. 1992, KA (KAC); 1 ex., same loc., 13. VI. 1993, KF (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 23. VIII. 1993, HY (EUMJ) 1 ex., same loc., 10. VI. 1995, KA (KAC); 1 ex., same loc., 26. V. 1999, KA (KAC); 2 exs., same loc., 2. X. 1999, KA (KAC); 1 ex., Kurakake-tôge, Fujiwarachô, 22.IX.1990, KA (KAC); 1 ex, same loc., 8.VII.2007, KA (KAC); 1 ex., same loc., 31.VII.2009, KA (KAC). [Shiga Pref.] 2 exs., Hôrai-san, Shiga-chô, 1. VII. 2001, KA (KAC); 1 ex., Oike-dake, Eigenji-chô, 18. V. 1997, KA (KAC). [Shimane Pref.] 1 ex., Azamiga-dake, Kakinoki-mura, Yoshika-chô, 10. VII. 2015, ST (KAC); 4 exs., Daimanji-san, Dôgo, 6. VI. 2016, HY (EUMJ). [Hiroshima Pref.] 2 exs., Hiwa-chô, 14. IX. 1975, SNA (HIWA). [Yamaguchi Pref.] 1 ex., Azamiga-take, Shûnan-shi, 21. V. 2015, SN (KAC); 2 exs., same loc., 24. VI. 2015, STA (KAC). <SHIKOKU> [Tokushima Pref.] 1 ex., Kôtsusan, Yamakawa-chô, 7. VIII. 1971, SK (EUMJ); 1 ex., Tsurugisan, Higashiiyayama-son, 11. VII. 1976, AO (EUMJ); 1 ex.,

Fig. 9. Larva of *Thymalus parviceps* Lewis. A, Habitus; B–D, head; E–G, urogomphi. Dorsal (A, B, E), ventral (C, F), and lateral (D, G) views.

same loc., 22. VII. 2000, KAI (EUMJ); 1 ex., Shibagoyama, Kamiyama-chô, 31. VII. 1975, MYO (EUMJ). [Ehime Pref.] 1 ex., Daiei-zan, Besshiyama-mura, 9. X. 1993, KO (EUMJ); 1 ex., Ishizuchi-san, 26. VIII. 1952, TIS (EUMJ); 2 exs., Komenono, Matsuyama-shi, 10. VI. 1973, GT (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 16. VII. 1975, AY (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 12. VI. 1976, YN (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 13. VI. 1976, YN (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 19. VIII. 1976, YN (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 19–24. IV. 1977, AO (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 7. IX. 1977, TMA (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 11. VI. 1993, KO (EUMJ); 1 male, same loc., 26. VII. 1993, KAI (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 1. VI. 1996, NO (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 17. V. 1997, SY (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 18. V. 2002, CT (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 22. V. 2004, RM (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 22. V. 2004, NO (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 3. VI. 2005, ST (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 3–4. VI. 2005, SHI (EUMJ); 7 exs., same loc., 31. V. 2009, RO (EUMJ); 1 ex., Takanawa-san, Matsuyama-shi, 28. VI. 1980, MKO (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 3. VIII. 1994, KAI (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 15. V. 2004, JY (EUMJ); 4 exs., same loc., 27. IX. 2007, TI (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 1. V. 2007, TI (EUMJ); 5 exs., same loc., 4. VIII. 1993, KO (EUMJ); 2 exs., Omogo-kei, Omogo-mura, 26. V. 1970, MT (EUMJ); 2 exs., same loc., 27. V. 1970, MT (EUMJ);

1 ex., same loc., 30–31. V. 1970, SK (EUMJ); 5 exs., Sakase, Omogo-mura, 2. VII. 1978, AO (EUMJ); 10 exs., Saragamine, Kuma-chô, 29. IV. 1962, SH (EUMJ); 3 exs., same loc., 4. IX. 1994, NO (EUMJ); 1 ex., Odamiyama, Oda-chô, 15. V. 1968, SH (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 16. VII. 1993, EY (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 19. VII. 1993, MK (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 19. VII. 1993, KO (EUMJ); 1 ex., same loc., 31. VII. 1994, KAI (EUMJ); 8 exs., Ônogahara, Nomura-chô, 18. XII. 1977, AO (EUMJ). [Kochi Pref.] 1 ex., Nishinogawa, Tosa-shi, 10. VII. 1961, MM (EUMJ). <KYUSHU> [Oita Pref.] 1 ex., Kuro-dake, Yufu-shi, 27. V. 2018, RI (KAC); 1 ex., same loc., 9. VI. 2019, RI (KAC); 1 ex., Takadoya-jinja, Minamitabar, Ume, Saiki-shi, 27. V. 2016, RI (KAC). [Kumamoto Pref.] 1 ex., Ichifusa-yama, Mizukami-mura, 8. VII. 1967, SH (EUMJ); 3 exs., Naidajjin-rindô, Yamato-chô, 8. VI. 2013, TYO (EUMJ). [Miyazaki Pref.] 1 ex., Shiraiwa-yama, Gokase-chô, 22. VII. 2016, TYO (EUMJ). [Kagoshima Pref.] 1 ex., Kurino-dake, Kurino-cho, 28. VII. 1974, MS (NSMT).

Specimens examined of larvae. 7 mature larvae, 2 pupae (EUMJ, in ethanol), Daimanji-san, Dogo, Oki, Shimane Pref., 21. V. 2019, HY. (A individual of larva was reared with host fungus and the adult was emerged in June 2019.)

Redescription. Male. Body (Fig. 1G, H) semicircular,

Fig. 10. Larva of *Thymalus parviceps* Lewis. A, Left mandible in ventral view; B, maxillae and labium in ventral view; C, antenna; D, labrum in dorsal view; E, epipharynx.

convex dorsally, flat ventrally, with strong metallic luster. Coloration of body brown to dark brown in dorsal surface, but darker in ventral surface; lateral margin transparent reddish brown; antennomeres 9–11 black; setae colorless.

Head roughly and irregularly punctate; vertex convex. Eyes relatively large, situated in lateral part of head. Antennae (Fig. 4E, F) relatively short; antennomere I longest, slightly curved interiorly, with gently arcuate outer margin; antennomeres III–V as long as wide respectively; antennomere VIII transverse, projecting laterally; antennomeres IX–XI densely covered with minute setae and sparsely with long setae; antennomere XI longer than wide approximate ratio of each antennomere ($n = 1$) as 6.7 : 1.7 : 1.3 : 1.2 : 1.3 : 1.2 : 1.2 : 1.0 : 2.2 : 2.2 : 3.5. Pronotum (Fig. 1I) irregularly, roughly and sparsely punctate less than *T. amamiensis*, irregularly and sparsely bearing short setae in mesal portion; lateral margins weakly upturned, densely bearing short setae; anterior angle rounded, strongly curved in distal portion; PW/PL 2.23–2.75 (2.46). Elytra regularly, roughly punctate similar to *T. amamiensis*, widest at below the middle, densely bearing short setae; lateral margins upturned, rounded in distal portion;

EL/EW 1.08–1.26 (1.15), EL/PL 3.58–4.33 (3.99), EW/PW 1.31–1.60 (1.42), TL/EW 1.35–1.61 (1.44). Abdominal ventrite V densely bearing long setae.

Tergite VIII (Fig. 5H) well sclerotized, trapezoidal, bearing short setae, almost straight in posterior margin. Sternite VIII (Fig. 5I) slightly sclerotized, bearing setae of irregular length, arcuate in posterior margin. Segments IX–X (Fig. 5J) with relatively short and stout median strut; posterior margin of segment X almost straight. Tegmen (Fig. 5K, L) short; phallobasic apodeme Y-shaped, short; tegminal strut short, subparallel-sided; parameral piece short, clearly shorter than tegminal strut, bearing short setae, shallowly excised at apical margin. Phallus (Fig. 5M, N) short, as long as tegmen, gently arcuate in dorsal margin, straight in ventral margin, relatively pointed at apex, widest at the middle.

Female. Sexual dimorphism indistinct; abdominal ventrite V sparsely bearing short setae; approximate ratio of each antennomere ($n = 1$) as 6.7 : 2.5 : 1.7 : 1.5 : 1.5 : 1.2 : 1.0 : 1.0 : 2.2 : 1.8 : 3.5. Tergite VIII (Fig. 6D) well sclerotized, trapezoidal, bearing short setae. Sternite VIII (Fig. 6E) moderately sclerotized, semicircular, bearing short setae,

Fig. 11. *Thymalus parviceps* (A–D) and *T. laticeps* (E–F). A, Adult in nature (Hokkaido); B, mature larva in nature (Shimane); C, habitat (Shimane); D, pupa in rearing; E, mature larva in nature (Shimane); F, adults in rearing.

shallowly concave in caudal margin; spiculum shorter than *T. laticeps*. Ovipositor (Fig. 6F) relatively short; stylus oblong, bearing setae of irregular length; approximate ratio of stylus, coxite, and baculus ($n = 1$) as 1.0 : 5.0 : 8.6.

Measurements ($n = 10$). TL 5.50–6.50 (6.19) mm; PW 2.80–3.30 (3.04) mm; PL 1.20–1.30 (1.24) mm; EL 4.30–5.20 (4.95) mm; EW 3.80–4.80 (4.32) mm.

Larvae (Figs. 9A, 11B). Body somewhat flattened dorsally, cream, weakly sclerotized except for well sclerotized head, mesal part of pronotum, and abdominal segment IX. Head

(Fig. 9B–D) well sclerotized, with five pairs of stemmata in antero-lateral parts. Mandibles (Fig. 10A) with two blunt apical teeth. Labrum (Fig. 10D, E) transverse, with four pairs of setae and one pair of pore; epipharynx with row of stout setae on anterior margin, with short setae and pores in mesal part. Antennae (Fig. 10C) 3-segmented; antennomere II as long as wide; antennomere III clearly longer than sensory appendix. Labium (Fig. 10B) transverse, with 2-segmented palpi. Prothorax (Fig. 9A) well sclerotized, bearing long setae in lateral parts. Meso- and Metathorax (Fig. 9A) wider than

prothorax, with 13 pairs of short setae and three pairs of long setae. Abdomen (Fig. 9A) bearing 12–16 pairs of setae; two lateral and one dorsal setae very long. Abdominal segment IX well sclerotized, densely bearing setae of irregular length. Urogomphi (Fig. 9E–G) relatively short, separated each other, having six projections; dorsal projection (d) short and oval, situated in basal part of dorsal surface, with two long and short setae; lateral projection (l) projecting postero-laterally, bearing a long seta; apical projection (a) longest, pointed at apex, projecting posteriorly, upturned in apical part, bearing short seta; subapical projection (s) long, pointed at apex, situated in ventral part of apical projection, with a long seta; inner projection (i) short, projecting interiorly; ventral projection (v) short, situated in base of subapical projection of ventral surface, bearing long seta.

Remarks. This species is similar to *T. amamiensis*, but distinguished from the latter by the short tegmen and phallus.

The larva of this species differs from the larva of *Thymalus laticeps* by the following characteristics: body somewhat flattened dorsally (thick in *T. laticeps*); abdomen bearing 12–16 pairs of setae (9–12 in *T. laticeps*); each urogomphus rather short, separated each other (long and close each other in *T. laticeps*); dorsal projection of urogomphus bearing two long setae (one long seta in *T. laticeps*).

Distribution. Japan (Hokkaido, Honshu, Oki, Shikoku, Kyushu); Sakhalin, Korea (including Chejudo).

Biological notes. This is common species. The adults are collected from various kinds of Polypores on decaying wood (Fig. 11A). In Shimane Prefecture, the larvae were collected from under fungus covered with rotten wood of deciduous tree in May (Fig. 11B, C), and pupated soon (Fig. 11D). The pupal period is a few days. Overwintering seems to be occurred in both adult and larval stages.

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References

- Asakawa, D. & H. Yoshitomi, 2019. A new species of the genus *Thymalus* (Coleoptera, Cleroidea, Thymalidae) from Taiwan. *Elytra, new series*, **9**: 77–80.
- Böving, A. G., & F. C. Craighead, 1931. An illustrated synopsis of the principal larval forms of the order Coleoptera. *Entomologica Americana, (n. ser.)*, **11**: 1–349.
- Chûjô, M. & C.-E. Lee, 1994. Trogositidae, Languriidae, Tenebrionidae and Alleculidae from Korea (incl. Chejudo Is.) (Coleoptera). *Esakia*, (34): 187–193.
- Crowson, R. A., 1964. A review of the classification of Cleroidea (Coleoptera), with descriptions of two new genera of Peltidae and of several new larval types. *Transactions of the Royal Entomological Society of London*, **116**: 275–327, 1 pl.
- Crowson, R. A., 1970. Further observations on Cleroidea (Coleoptera). *Proceedings of the Royal Entomological Society of London, Series B*, **39**: 1–20.
- Gimmel, M. L., M. Bocakova, N. Gunter & R. A. B. Leschen, 2019. Comprehensive phylogeny of the Cleroidea (Coleoptera: Cucujiformia). *Systematic Entomology*, **44**: 527–558.
- Hayashi, N., 1950. The beetles from food-fungus *Fomes pinicola*, with some ecological notes. *Kontyu*, **18**: 27–28.
- Hayashi, N., 1952. Larva and pupa of *Thymalus laticeps* Lewis (Temnochilidae Col.) (Studies on Mycetophagous beetles IV). *New Entomologist*, **2**: 12–15. (In Japanese, with English title.)
- Kawanabe, M. & M. Miyatake, 1996. A redescription of *Xylographella punctata* (Coleoptera, Ciidae), with description of a new tribe. *Elytra*, **24**: 125–130.
- Kimura, F., 1995. Breeding and display of fungivorous beetles at Kashihara City Insectarium. *Insectarium*, **32**: 314–317. (In Japanese.)
- Kolibáč, J., 2005. A review of the Trogositidae [sic!]. Part 1: Morphology of the genera (Coleoptera, Cleroidea). *Entomologica Basiliensia et Collectionis Frey*, **27**: 39–159.
- Kolibáč, J., 2006. A review of the Trogositidae Part 2: Larval morphology, phylogeny and taxonomy (Coleoptera, Cleroidea). *Entomologica Basiliensia et Collectionis Frey*, **28**: 105–153.
- Kolibáč, J., 2013. Trogositidae: A review of the beetle family, with a catalogue and keys. *ZooKeys*, **366**: 1–194.
- Latreille, P. A., 1802. Histoire Naturelle, Générale et Particulière des Crustacés et Insectes. Tom troisième: 133. (x+467pp+1).
- Lewis, G., 1894. On new species of Trogositidae from Japan. *The Entomologist's Monthly Magazine*, **30**: 32–34.
- Miyatake, M., 1985. Trogositidae [pp. 147–150, pl.24]. In: Kurosawa Y., S. Hisamatsu & H. Sasaji (eds.) *The Coleoptera of Japan in Color*, 3. 514. Hoikusha, Osaka. (In Japanese, with English book title.)
- Nakane, T., 1963. Trogositidae [sic!]. In: Nakane T. Ohbayashi K. & Kurosawa Y. (eds), *Iconographia Insectorum Japonicorum Colore Naturali Edita 2*: 181–182, pl. 91. Hokuryu-kan. (In Japanese.)
- Oogai, H., 2014. Beetles newly recorded from Okinawa-honto (part 1). *Gekkan-mushi*, (518): 44–45. (In Japanese.)
- Sato, M., 2002. Notes on the genus *Iwawakia*, with description of a new species from central Japan. *Japanese Journal of systematic Entomology*, **8**: 109–114.
- Suzuki, T., 2009. The Handbook of Rotten Wood Biodiversity. 88 pp., Bun-ichi Sogo Shuppan, Tokyo. (In Japanese.)
- Yoshitomi, H., 2014. *Phanodesta celebessa* (Coleoptera: Trogositidae): A new species from Sulawesi, Indonesia. *Japanese Journal of Systematic Entomology*, **20**: 219–223.
- Yoshitomi, H., & C. F. Lee, 2014. A revision of the genus *Kolibacia* Leschen and Lackner (Coleoptera, Trogositidae). *Entomological Science*, **17**: 240–250.

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